

Demographic Profile, Clinical Presentation and Outcome in Acute Poisoning Patients: Retrospective StudyM.R. Kiran Kumar¹, S. Ramya Krishna², G. Sarada³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore²Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore³Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore

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Abstract:**Aim:** To explore the demographic, etiological, clinical characteristics & outcome of cases presented to emergency department with poisoning.**Materials & Methods:** This retrospective study conducted at ACSR Govt Medical College. Totally data from medical records of 100 patients with OP poisoning were retrieved. Clinical, demographical & laboratory investigation were recorded. Glasgow coma scale (GCS) & Poisoning severity score (PSS) were estimated within 24 hours of admission.**Results:** Higher poisoning seen in Males (71%) than females (29%), and most commonly seen in the age group of 21-30 years (59%) where pre-hospitalization period was <6 hours in most of the patients (67%). Significant association was observed between GCS (P<0.001), PSS (P<0.001) & outcome of OP poisoning. No significant association was observed with pseudocholinesterase level and OP poisoning severity. A total of 83% patients were improved after treatment and mortality rate observed was 17%. Out of these 83% severe complications were observed in 14% of the cases. Suicidal poisoning is the major cause of poisoning in majority cases.**Conclusion:** Current study shows that both GCS & PSS were similar in predicting the outcome whereas pseudo cholinesterase levels which was used as mainstay approach to assess the prognosis shows no significance at all. GCS being less time consuming and can be done easily can be used in peripheral areas to identify high risk patients for urgent referral to tertiary care centers. It has shown that usage of certain compounds like chlorpyrifos and methyl parathion can be reduced to reduce the morbidity and mortality rate.**Keywords:** Organophosphorus compounds, acetylcholine esterase, Glasgow coma scale, Poisoning severity score.

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Introduction

Organophosphorus compounds are pesticides that inhibit cholinesterase and are organic derivatives of phosphoric and phosphonic acid. These compounds cause phosphorylation of the acetylcholine esterase (AChE) enzyme rendering it inactive. Except with early pharmaceutical intervention, the OP compound's binding to enzyme is irreversible.

Inactive phosphorylated AChE is unable to hydrolyse Ach leading to its accumulation in the neuronal synapses & neuromuscular junctions [1] clinical manifestations of OP compounds poisoning are as a result of an overabundance of acetylcholine at the muscarinic and nicotinic receptors in a syndrome of cholinergic crisis [1]. Poisoning with OP compounds is a common toxicological emergency in an agricultural country like India because of its ease of availability. According to WHO reports, pesticides ingestion is now the most popular means of suicide worldwide [2]. WHO

documents pesticide toxicity as a prevalent global problem, associated with over two lakh deaths in a year, most poisonings occur in Southeast parts of Asia. As per NCRB report, 28% of suicides in India were committed by consuming poisons in the year 2015. Out of all pesticide related deaths, poisoning with OP compounds account for 2/3rd of all deaths [3]. It has become common medical & social problem worldwide causing significant morbidity & mortality [4].

In developing countries mortality can be as high as 70%. This could be probably because of lack of hospital services in vicinity, inadequate transport facility, delay in initiation of appropriate treatment and non-availability of definite antidote [5]. In many cases early assessment by clinical markers is essential to categorize the severity and early referral to higher center where aggressive treatment can be initiated immediately. Many studies have

been conducted to investigate the diagnostic and prognostic value of serum cholinesterase levels in OP poisoning and their relationship with neurological syndrome [6]. Most of the studies have shown that, though serum cholinesterase can be used as a diagnostic marker, it has minimal role as a prognostic marker [7]. Poisoning severity score (PSS) is normally done at admission and at frequent intervals during hospital stay. Usually, grading takes into consideration only observed clinical symptoms and signs, rather than those that might be anticipated [8]. PSS can be used to predict the outcome of poisoning patients if it is documented at the time of admission.

The GCS is a neurological scale that tries to provide a reliable objective method of documenting a person's conscious status for initial and subsequent evaluation. It is considered as best indicator to assess severity, including mortality caused by OP compound poisoning in an emergency. Many studies are available like GCS score, APACHE II score, LDH, serum immunoglobulins, circulating complements, CPK and various other scoring systems, to assess severity of OP compound poisoning. But, there is no agreement regarding these factors to determine severity and to predict morbidity & mortality [9]. Current study aimed to explore the demographic, etiological, clinical characteristics and outcome of cases presented to our emergency department with poisoning.

Material and Methods

Study Design: Retrospective study.

Inclusion Criteria: All the patients presented to the emergency department, ACSR GMC/GGH Nellore with acute poisoning of all types.

Study Area: Department of Emergency medicine, ACSR GMC/GGH Nellore

Study Subjects: All Patients with acute poisoning of all types presented to Emergency Medicine.

Data Collection: Retrospectively data was collected from the Medical records of last 6 months and entered into a pre-structured proforma.

Statistical Analysis:

Data was recorded in a Microsoft Excel sheet. Descriptive data was presented as mean & standard

deviation or median for continuous variables, and as frequencies or percentages for categorical variables. Continuous variables were compared using Student's T-test. Categorical variables were compared using Chi-square test. Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS statistical software 22.0 version. P value less than 0.05 is considered as statistically significant.

Results

The majority of poisonings occurred in the 21-30 age group (n=56), followed by the 31-40 age group (n=19), and the 18-20 age group (n=11). The oldest patient is 67 years old, while the youngest is only 18 yrs old & Patients under the age of 18 are not eligible to participate in the study. The majority of patients (n=76) were men. There were 24 female patients. 71 patients reached the hospital in less than 6 hour of poison consumption. 20 cases came to the hospital in 7-12 hours. None patients reached the hospital after >12 hour of poison consumption. In 34 cases, the identity of the op substance was unknown, and the diagnosis was determined based on clinical signs and symptoms of op poisoning. The most commonly consumed compound was Methyl parathion, whereas the least commonly ingested compounds were Phosphoran & Trizophos, Monocrotophas. Around half of the patients drank less than 50 ml of poison. Between 50 & 100 mL were drunk by 32 patients. 98% cases were due to the ingestion of OP compounds with suicidal intent and 2% cases are due to inhalation. 83% were non-alcoholics & 17% of study participants are alcoholics. In 45 study participants, levels are < 500. In 19 patients, levels are between 500-1000. In 23 patients, levels are between 1000-5000 and levels are >5000 in 13 patients. There were 48 cases of grade I poisoning, 27 of grade II poisoning, 21 of grams. III poisoning and 4 cases of grade IV where death occurs in less than the 24 hours. GCS scores were <10 in 27 study participants at admission and in 24 study participants after 24 hrs of hospital admission. GCS scores were >10 in 73 study participants at admission and in 76 study participants after 24 hrs of hospital admission. 27 patients were intubated in total, out of which most of them were intubated within the first 2 days of admission. 72 cases recovered with no intubation. 13 cases recovered with requirement of intubation and prolonged ICU stay and 15 cases were expired.

Table 1: Distribution of the day of intubation, Outcome and Complications of study participants

Day of intubation	Number of patients(n=100)	Percentage (%)
No intubation	73	73.0
One to Two days	23	23.0
Three to Five days	4	4.0
Outcome		
Survived without intubation	72	72.0
Survived on intubation	13	13.0

Death	15	15.0
Complications		
No Complications	94	94.0
Intermediate syndrome	2	2.0
Status epilepticus	2	2.0
Delayed op compound induced neuropathy	1	1.0
VAP	1	1.0

Table 2: Association between age, sex, OPC compound, amount of OPC, Pseudocholinesterase levels, Poison severity Grading, GCS & outcome

	Outcome			Total	P value	
	Survived without intubation	Survived on intubation	Death			
Age (in yrs)						
18-20	11(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	11	0.03	
21-30	42(75.0%)	8(14.3%)	6(10.7%)	56		
31-40	13(68.4%)	3(15.8%)	3(15.8%)	19		
41-50	3(60.0%)	1(20.0%)	1(20.0%)	5		
51-60	3(42.9%)	1(14.3%)	3(42.9%)	7		
61-70	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	2		
Sex						
Male	54(71.1%)	10(13.2%)	12(15.8%)	76		
Female	18(75.0%)	3(12.5%)	3(12.5%)	24		
OPC compound						
Clorporphyros	14(87.5%)	1(6.3%)	1(6.3%)	16	<0.05	
Diazinon	4(50.0%)	2(25.0%)	2(25.0%)	8		
Dichlorvos	4(57.1%)	2(28.6%)	1(14.3%)	7		
Dimethoate	4(80.0%)	1(20.0%)	0(0.0%)	5		
Metacid	5(55.6%)	2(22.2%)	2(22.2%)	9		
Methylparathion	12(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	12		
Monocrotophos	1(50.0%)	0(0.0%)	1(50.0%)	2		
Phosphoran	1(50.0%)	0(0.0%)	1(50.0%)	2		
Quinalphos	2(66.7%)	1(33.3%)	0(0.0%)	3		
Trizhophos	0(0.0%)	1(50.0%)	1(50.0%)	2		
Unknown	25(73.5%)	3(8.8%)	6(17.6%)	34		
Amount of OPC taken (in ml)						
<50 ml	38(86.4%)	4(9.1%)	2(4.5%)	44		<0.05
50-100ml	17(53.1%)	6(18.8%)	9(28.1%)	32		
>100 ml	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	2		
Unknown	17(77.3%)	1(4.5%)	4(18.2%)	22		
Pseudocholinesterase levels						
<500	31(68.9%)	8(17.8%)	6(13.3%)	45	0.378	
500-1000	16(84.2%)	2(10.5%)	1(5.3%)	19		
1000-5000	14(60.9%)	3(13.0%)	6(26.1%)	23		
>5000	11(84.6%)	0(0.0%)	2(15.4%)	13		
Poison severity score Grading						
I	47(97.9%)	1(2.1%)	0(0.0%)	48	<0.0001	
II	24(88.9%)	0(0.0%)	3(11.1%)	27		
III	1(4.8%)	12(57.1%)	8(38.1%)	21		
IV	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	4(100.0%)	4		
GCS score at admission						
<10	6(22.2%)	12(44.4%)	9(33.3%)	27	<0.0001	
>10	66(90.4%)	1(1.4%)	6(8.2%)	73		
GCS score after 24 hrs						
<10	1(4.2%)	11(45.8%)	12(50.0%)	24	<0.0001	
>10	71(93.4%)	2(2.6%)	3(3.9%)	76		

Discussion

The mean age of patients was 31.5±10.8 years. The majority of patients reported to the emergency department were in the age range of 21-30 years. The youngest patient is 20 years old and the oldest is 66 years old.

This study's demographics are consistent with prior research by Akdur et al [10]. These findings are detrimental to society because the majority of the population is young, and this young population contributes significantly to the country's output while also having no co-morbidities.

In our study population, Males made up 76% of the patients and females made up only 24 %. Male preponderance was seen in Kishore thunga et al [11], and Nilamadhab et al [12].

The median was 5 hours and the mean difference in time lapse was 6.5 ± 4.8 hours. Banerjee et al [13] found that the average pre-hospitalization period was 4 hours.

When compared to the other studies, this one had a longer average pre-hospitalization time. Location and transportation measures are two elements that can be blamed for the significant delay. The majority of patients are referred from a lower level facility where primary care measures (e.g. stomach wash, first dose of atropine, etc.) are used to control the poisoning effects to some extent. These procedures may cause a delay in the patient's arrival to our facility.

The diagnosis was predicated on a history of pesticide use, the smell of OP compounds, and clinical characteristics induced by cholinergic excess. Methyl Chlorpyrifos and Parathion were the most commonly consumed compounds. Triazophos, Phosphoran, and Monocrotophos were the least used compounds. In other studies, methyl parathion was the most commonly consumed chemical [11,13]. A total of 44% of the patients had consumed less than 50ml of OP compound poison and 2% patients arrived with >100 ml of op compound poison in their systems. The amount of poison consumed has not been established in studies by Akdur et al. The majority of other study, too, failed to disclose the amount of toxin consumed.

Pseudo cholinesterase levels were below 500 in 45 percent of the patients, and between 500 and 1000 in 19%. Around 23% of the patients had levels between 1000 and 5000, while 13% had levels greater than 5000. In cases of op compound poisoning, pseudocholine esterase levels are regularly tested.

The poison severity score was recorded on admission and 24 hours later, and the worst value was used as the final poison severity score in this

investigation. There were 48 grade 1 instances in the study, 27 grade 2 cases, 21 grade 3 cases, and four grade 4 or death cases.

GCS was measured at the time of admission and again after 24 hours. At the time of admission, 27 patients had GCS scores of 10 or less, and 24 patients had GCS scores of 10 or less after 24 hours. At the time of admission, 73 patients had GCS scores of 10 or higher and 76 patients had GCS scores of 10 or higher after 24 hrs.

The distribution of patients according to the day of intubation is shown in Table 11. Intubation was not required in 73% of the patients. Out of the remaining 27% of patients, 23% were intubated during the first two days, and another four were intubated between days three and five. During the cholinergic crisis phase of OP compound poisoning, the majority of patients who were intubated had to be intubated within the first two days. According to a study by Davis et al [14], intubation at admission or within the first 24 hours was highly specific for mortality.

In our study, 72% of the patients survived without intubation, 13% survived but required intubation and a longer stay in the ICU, and 15% of the patients died. When compared to prior investigations by Akdur et al, and Davis et al [14], the percentage of mortality in this study was higher.

Patients who survived without intubation had a mean age of 27.3±8.3, patients who survived but needed intubation had a mean age of 33.86±12.34, and patients who died had a mean age of 38±14.56. Hence, the relationship between age and the outcome of op poisoning was significant (p=0.001). Sex was not observed to be related to the results of op chemical poisoning (p=0.587). This research backs up the conclusions of prior investigations by Akdur et al, & Davis et al. There was significant association observed between prehospitalization and the outcome of postoperative chemical poisoning (p=0.003). Because delaying therapy allows the toxin to reach its original peak serum level, irreversibly damaging tissue.

In this study, we were unable to association any specific compound to a negative outcome. However, methyl parathion (n=2) was the most common cause of death, followed by chlorpyrifos (n=1).

Hence, prohibiting or restricting the use of these substances may reduce morbidity and death in op poisoning patients. The amount of poison taken was observed to have a substantial relationship with the outcome of op compound poisoning. The consequences become considerably harsher as the amount of poison taken increases. However, this cannot be accepted at face value since, while the

amount of poison matters, the type of poison and its potency also play a role. A poison that is highly potent and lethal may require less poison to produce greater harm. There was no statistical association seen between alcohol use and the occurrence of op compound poisoning.

There was no significant association between pseudo cholinesterase levels and the outcomes of op compound poisoning ($p=0.378$). The association between n-acetyl cholinesterase level and the severity of OP poisoning has been investigated in earlier studies comparable to this one, but no consensus has emerged. We found no association between pseudo cholinesterase levels and the result of op poisoning in our research. In fact, patients who died had higher mean pseudo choline esterase levels than those who survived intubation.

Except for one patient who presented with grade 1 poisoning, all of the patients lived without the need for intubation. Patients with grade 2 poisoning survived 88.9% of the time without intubation, while 11.1% were died. Patients with grade 3 poisoning had a 4.8% chance of surviving without intubation, a 57.1% chance of surviving with intubation, and a 38.1 percent chance of dying. The goal of our research was to see if there was an association between the poison severity score within the first 24 hours and the outcome of acute poisoning.

The current study observed an association between the degree of poisoning within the first 24 hours and the result of op compound poisoning, ($p<0.001$). This supports prior research by Davis et al, and Akdur et al. GCS of 10 was observed to have a strong relationship with the outcome of op poisoning in the current investigation, both at admission ($p=0.001$) and after 24 hours of admission ($p=0.001$). The worst outcome was given a GCS of 10. Although a GCS score of 8 is commonly seen as a signal for intubation. In our study, intubation and mechanical ventilator assistance were only considered when the patient suffered respiratory failure (RF), not based on GCS scores. This conclusion is significant since GCS is simple, simple to use, and can be used in remote locations with limited infrastructure.

Current study findings demonstrate the utility of a few clinical indices, such as the GCS and Poisoning Severity Scoring Systems, in predicting severity, which can then be used to predict the outcome of poisoning in patients, particularly during triage. Early detection of the severity, followed by rapid treatment, can help to prevent late respiratory and cardiac failures caused by OP compound poisoning.

Conclusion

The GCS & PSS scoring systems were found to be useful in predicting the severity and outcome of OP compound poisoning in this analysis. There was no association between plasma pseudo cholinesterase levels at the time of admission and the result of OP compound poisoning. The most often taken chemicals, methyl parathion and chlorpyrifos, are responsible for the majority of deaths. Hence, prohibiting or restricting their use may reduce op compound poisoning mortality and morbidity.

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